

Speculation on the Role of Spin in Momentum Based Energy

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Physics is based on experimental observables. Some of these observables are functions of other observables. For example, mass is an observable associated with inertia or gravity and velocity is classically measured, but the product mv yields nonrelativistic momentum which may be measured independently through an impulse hit with a target. A further issue with measurement is the case of vectors. For a vector pointing in one direction, one may orient the z axis to lie along this direction. If one always does this, momentum appears as a scalar, but one has to continuously rotate the co-ordinate system to account for different orientations. In this note, we are interested in spin which is linked to a kind of rotation and so we focus on the momentum vector, but only consider a function of momentum which yields a linear E , free particle energy. Thus, for the Lorentz invariant: $E^2 - p \cdot p = m^2 c^2$, we consider the nonrelativistic limit: $E = p^2 / 2m$.

In quantum mechanics, a free particle is represented by the complex probability (wavefunction) $\exp(ip \cdot r)$. This function has physical implications as it manifests itself in n -slit interference experiments so it is physical (not a mathematical convenience), but at the same time is responsible for conservation of momentum in x, y, z because $\int dx \exp(ip_1 x) \exp(ip_2 x) = 0$ if p_1 is not equal to p_2 . A physical function (property) through orthogonality creates an important relationship, namely conservation of momentum. We suggest that a similar idea may be at work in a relationship linking a linear E (free particle energy) to a function of momentum.

We start with a linear E related to a function of p and only focus on the p vector because if it is treated as a number, the co-ordinate axis must rotate to account for its orientation. We only consider a situation in which $p(x)$, $p(y)$ and $p(z)$ behave in an independent manner in the function of p (i.e. in the same manner as p itself) and suggest that instead of using vector analysis, there should exist a physical co-ordinate axis for each projection $p(x)$, $p(y)$ and $p(z)$ if they are independent. We argue that $p \cdot p = p(x)p(x) + p(y)p(y) + p(z)p(z)$ does not contain cross terms such as $p(x)p(y)$. This is a kind of orthogonality which we associate with a rotational kind of operator linked with the $p(i)$ operator $-i\hbar/dx(i)$. In other words, we seek: p vector = generalized number = $p(x)s_x + p(y)s_y + p(z)s_z$, where $s(i)$ are generalized numbers or matrices, so that when this multiplied by itself, it yields $p \cdot p$. It turns out that the $s(i)$ are the 2×2 Pauli matrices.

In the case of a photon, there is no nonrelativistic limit and a linear E equation related to p is: $E = |p|c$. This equation is not independent in $p(x)$, $p(y)$, $p(z)$ i.e. one cannot write $p(x)s_x + p(y)s_y + p(z)s_z$ and obtain $E = \{p(x)s_x + p(y)s_y + p(z)s_z\} c$. Thus we look for another equation containing a linear E and a function of p . In this case, we use energy and momentum densities as given by the continuity equation: $d/dt \text{ partial energy density} + d \text{ grad} \cdot E \times B = 0$ where d is a constant and E and B electric and magnetic 3-vectors. As in the above analysis, one wishes to have a momentum operator linked with a kind of rotational operator which allows one to eliminate vector math and use generalized numbers. In such a case, grad in the continuity equation becomes the momentum vector and ϵ_{ijk} (Levi-Civita symbol in the cross product) becomes the spin matrix.

Thus in both cases, spin governs the form of the function containing momentum which yields a linear E. In other words, it is not momentum alone which yields the relationship between a linear E (free particle energy) and momentum.

Observables in Physics

Physics is based on the measurement of observables, but sometimes functions of observables lead to a new observable which may be independently measured. For example, rest mass, m_0 , may be measured through its inertial effects (a force is needed to start it in motion) or through gravitational effects. Velocity may also be measured classically. Nonrelativistic momentum $m_0 v$ may also be measured independently of m_0 and v through an impulse hit on a target. Thus $p = m_1 v_1 = m_2 v_2$ etc lead to the same impulse hit.

Here we consider the situations of a momentum vector and try to understand the meaning of a vector.. If the p vector lies always along the z axis, then momentum appears as a scalar, but the co-ordinate system has to rotate to account for different orientations. Specifically, the co-ordinate system rotates for each orientation. Thus, if one considers p to be a number, then it is associated with a rotation of the co-ordinate axes.

We consider the case for which an expression linear in E is linked with a function of p . We consider a rest mass and note that $-E^2 + p \cdot p = -m_0^2 c^2$ is not linear in E , but the nonrelativistic result of this, $E = p \cdot p / 2m_0$ is. We use this equation and demand that $p(x)$, $p(y)$ and $p(z)$ appear in the same form as total p . If p lies along the z axis, then $p \cdot p = p^2$. Alternatively, one has $p(x)p(x) + p(y)p(y) + p(z)p(z)$. This is of the same form for each as p^2 . The independence contains no cross terms (that is why it is independent). We suggest that given that p values appear, one needs a p operator acting on a wavefunction, but also a rotational kind of operator which allows $p(x)$, $p(y)$, and $p(z)$ to appear as independent systems. The elimination of cross terms suggests a kind of orthogonality between the rotational operators.

In other words, we do not use vector analysis to solve this problem, but insist on the orthogonality arising from a physical property. A main reason for this assertion is the free particle wavefunction form $\exp(-iEt + i p \cdot r)$. This physical form ensures orthogonality for different p values. For example, if one has two wavefunctions, $\exp(ip_1 z)$ and $\exp(ip_2 z)$ then:

$$\int dx \exp(-ip_1 z) \exp(ip_2 z) = 0 \quad (4)$$

Thus the wavefunction form $\exp(ipz)$ is not only physical, but it physically ensures orthogonality of different momentum states, i.e. conservation of momentum. One would need an operator $V(x)$ (e.g. a potential) to provide the impulse hit necessary to allow p_1 to become p_2 . If conservation of momentum is achieved through such an orthogonality, we argue that the orthogonality associated with the non-mixing of $p(x)$ with $p(y)$, for example, in creating energy should also follow from a physical state. Such a state is associated with an operator, for example one linked with rotation as each $p(x)$, $p(y)$, $p(z)$ has its own rotated co-ordinate axis system. As a result, one needs to go beyond vector analysis and suggest a physical reason for the orthogonal result: $p \cdot p = p(x)p(x) + p(y)p(y) + p(z)p(z)$. Given that free particle energy is based on momentum

squared (nonrelativistic case), the operator for p must appear and we suggest that it should be linked with a rotational type operator to ensure orthogonality i.e.

$$A = p(x) s_x + p(y) s_y + p(z) s_z \quad ((5))$$

Such that: A times $A = p(x)p(x) + p(y)p(y) + p(z)p(z)$ ((6)) consistent with p times p , where p is the momentum magnitude. A solution is to have s_x , s_y , and s_z represent the 2×2 Pauli matrices for which:

$$s_x s_x = s_y s_y = s_z s_z = 1 \text{ and } s_x s_y + s_y s_x = s_x s_z + s_z s_x = s_y s_z + s_z s_y = 0 \quad ((7))$$

Just as $\exp(ip \cdot z')$ may be written as $\exp(ip(x) x) \exp(ip(y) y) \exp(ip(z) z)$ where x' is the z -axis of a specially oriented co-ordinate system and one has conservation of not only p , but $p(x)$, $p(y)$ and $p(z)$ due to the orthogonality of the $\exp(ipx)$ form, a similar result should hold for the $p(x)$, $p(y)$, $p(z)$ case when one considers free particle energy. In the case of free particle energy, which is a scalar, this is achieved through the Pauli matrices. If one examines the eigenvectors of s_z , namely $(1,0)$ and $(0,1)$, one sees that they may be interpreted as rotation in one direction or the other (suggesting a rest frame). We suggest that the quadratic exclusion of cross terms, such as $p(x)p(y)$, is identical to the idea of the exclusion of quadratic cross terms $\exp(ipx) \exp(ip1x)$ when one integrates over x . The only difference is that one considers operators here as one is creating energy from momentum.

We have argued before that $\exp(ipx)$ follows from translational invariance and the s_x , s_y , s_z matrices from a kind of rotational invariance, but in the latter case there are other issues involved as described by the constraints above, i.e. a linear E and $p(x)$, $p(y)$ and $p(z)$ behaving in the same manner as p total in a function linked to linear E . Thus there is some kind of rotational motion associated with rotational invariance which governs or restricts the form of free particle energy written in terms of momentum. This holds both nonrelativistically and relativistically.

Case of a Photon

A photon satisfies the relativistic equation $E^2 = p \cdot p c^2$, i.e. the Lorentz invariant equation $-E^2 + p \cdot p = -m_0^2 c^4$ with $m_0=0$. We, however, seek an equation linear in E , such that $p(x)$, $p(y)$ and $p(z)$ appear in the same form as p total. $E=|p|c$ is not consistent with such independence i.e. $p(x)c + p(y)c + p(z)c$ is not $|p|c$ even if one inserts some kind of rotational matrices.

Does this mean that there is no spin associated with a photon, i.e. no rotational invariance and corresponding rotational motion? In the above section, we argued that the Pauli 2×2 matrices acted as spin operators which dictated the form of the $p \cdot p = p(x)p(x) + p(y)p(y) + p(z)p(z)$. In the nonrelativistic case, this is associated with a linear free particle energy E . To continue the analogy, one might consider an equation which links energy density and momentum density for a photon and includes rotational invariance. We rejected $E^2 = p \cdot p c^2$, but may consider energy and momentum density instead. In such a case, one has:

$$d/dt \text{ partial } aE \cdot E + b B \cdot B + d \text{ grad } (\text{partial}) \cdot E \times B = 0 \quad ((8))$$

$$d/dt \text{ partial Energy density} + \text{grad dot momentum density} = 0$$

A,b,c are constants and E and B, 3-vector electric and magnetic fields. It seems that rotational invariance exists for both energy density and momentum density. The energy density form is associated with a dot product which does not mix E(x) E(y) terms etc (and the same for B). Such a dot product should be associated with the Pauli matrices, it seems according to the arguments given in above sections. The argument in the above sections, however, was that a vector, namely the p vector, may be treated as a scalar if one considers rotations of the co-ordinate system. This same idea holds here except for the fact that one wishes to find a rotation type operator associated with a p operator i.e. -id/dx as in the above arguments for a particle with rest mass. Energy was associated with p dot p which implies d/dx d/dx. The grad term in ((8)) (associated with momentum density) is in the exact form as the momentum operator and so one may obtain a spin matrix from the cross product i.e.

$$E \times B \text{ (i)} = e_{ijk} E(j) B(k) \quad ((9)) \text{ where } e_{ijk} \text{ is the Levi-Civita symbol}$$

This becomes a matrix if i denotes the matrix and jk the elements. Thus one may factor out E+iB from ((8)) such that: (E+iB)* dot (E+iB) = energy density to obtain a linear equation with d/dt associated with E+iB and a term e_{ijk} d/dx(j) (E+iB) (k). Then E+iB becomes the wavefunction. The spin matrix e_{ijk} again dictates the form of momentum density, i.e. d E x B, which is directly linked to energy density ((8)).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider three points. First, we note that the free particle form exp(ip dot r), which follows as a kind of square root of translational invariance, leads to conservation of momentum. First, if one rotates the co-ordinate system so that p lies along z, then Integral exp(-ip z) exp(ip1z) dz= 0 unless p1=p. Alternatively, one has conservation of momentum in the x,y and z directions if one uses exp(ipx)exp(ipy)exp(ipz). exp(i p dot r) is not simply a mathematical function, it has observable physical features (n-slit interference).

Secondly, we look for an expression linking p directly to a linear E. The Lorentz invariant -EE+p dot p = -momo does not do this for a particle with rest mass, but the nonrelativistic form E=pp/2mo (free particle) does (and spin also exists in a nonrelativistic situation. Next, we consider that if one wishes to treat p (momentum) as a number (i.e. always lying along the z axis), one has to rotate the co-ordinate system for each orientation. Thus, a linear vector seems to be automatically linked with rotation. This, we argue, explains why in the Dirac equation it is the momentum operator which is linked with Pauli matrices (within a 4x4 matrix) and why in the continuity equation for a photon ExB (electric and magnetic fields) are linked with a spin matrix associated with the Levi-Civita symbol.

Thirdly, we insist that p(x), p(y) and p(z) in the equation linking a linear E to a function of ptotal behave in the same way as ptotal. This independence then treats p(x), p(y) and p(z) as having

their own co-ordinate axes or spin operator which creates independence through orthogonality. The spin operator (matrix), however, is associated with a physical state.

The goal is to use these conditions and to try to treat momentum as a number. For a quantum free particle, this leads to an operator $-i\hbar/dx$ yielding momentum when acting on a wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$. We suggest that there should exist another operator linked with rotation which allows $p(x)$, $p(y)$ and $p(z)$ to act as independent systems in the linear E function of p. For $E=pp/2m$, one may use: $p = p(x)s_x+p(y)s_y+p(z)s_z$. For p multiplied by p to yield p dot p, one must have $s_x s_x = s_y s_y = s_z s_z = 1$ and $s(i)s(j)+s(j)s(i)=0$ if i is not equal to j. The 2x2 Pauli matrices satisfy this condition. $E=pp/2m$ is a nonrelativistic result which follows from $-EE+p \cdot p = -m^2 c^4$ for a particle with rest mass.

The linear E equation for a photon is $E = |p|c$. This equation does not treat $p(x)$, $p(y)$ and $p(z)$ as independent, i.e. $|p|c$ is not equal to $p(x)c+p(y)c+p(z)c$ even if one were to insert rotational matrices. Thus for a photon a different equation is needed. We suggest instead the continuity equation: $d/dt \text{ partial (energy density)} + d \text{ grad dot } E \times B$. We only consider rotational invariance linked with the momentum term and try to write this as a product of momentum operator and rotational type of matrix. The momentum operator follows from the grad and the spin operator from ϵ_{ijk} (which appears in the cross product).

Thus we argue that spin creates the form of momentum which is used in a function set equal to a linear E (energy term) for a free particle or photon.